

Irbid-Jordan, October 1st - 4th 2024

Evaluating the Structural Performance of 3D Printed FRCC Beams with Anchoring Reinforcement: Material, Geometry, and Loading Perspectives

Bara'a R. Alnemrawi

Jordan University of Science and Technology (JUST), Jordan

Rajai Z. Al-Rousan

Jordan University of Science and Technology (JUST), Jordan

Khairedin M. Abdalla

Jordan University of Science and Technology (JUST), Jordan

Nikos D. Lagaros

National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Greece

Jordan, 1 Oct. 2024

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Research significance

1

Increasing attention was paid to three-dimensional (3D) printing technology in the construction, architecture, and medical care sectors

2

The utilization of cementitious composites in 3D concrete printing was increased to upgrade the structural behavior of the printed members

3

In contrast, difficulties and uncertainties still exist regarding the reinforcement method of the printed members with other induced challenges regarding the cost efficiency and sustainability concerns

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Research significance

4

This study evaluates the structural performance of 3D printed beams with fiber-reinforced cementitious composite (FRCC) and anchoring reinforcement using the method of finite element analysis (FEA)

5

A total of eighteen beams were simulated with different shear spans (400, 500, and 575 mm), overall depth (120, 200, and 276 mm), and FRCC compressive strengths (23.2 and 43.2 MPa)

6

The behavior was reported for all models in terms of the ultimate load and its corresponding deflection, initial stiffness, toughness, and failure modes

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Experimental Work Review

The flexural behavior of 3D printed beams made of FRCC concrete was experimentally carried out by Cai et al. using a total of five specimens. The behavior between the 3D printed and traditional beams was compared along with examining the efficiencies of different reinforcement configurations. Specimens were of 1600 mm length, 200 mm height, and 120 mm width with all beams having constant longitudinal and transverse reinforcement ratios of 0.011% and 0.018%, respectively.

Three types of reinforcement were examined (joint reinforcement, anchoring reinforcement, and inserted steel reinforcement) with the anchoring reinforcement type showing higher efficiency. The FRCC cementitious matrix was made of PE fibers with 6 mm length and 24 mm diameter resulting in a 23.2 MPa compressive strength mixture. The printed beams were cast using the layer-by-layer technique with various methodologies depending on the installed reinforcement type. The beam geometry and reinforcement details are presented in **Fig. 1**.

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Experimental Work Review

Fig. 1.
Beam
detailing

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Material modeling and element types

The finite element modeling was utilized to fulfill the objectives of this study using ABAQUS software. The FRCC was modeled using the (C3D8R) element while steel reinforcement was simulated using the (T3D2) element. Beams were simulated using the four-point loading with a 400 mm distance between each two constitutive steel plates. The geometry and the reinforcement details of the conventional and the printed beams are illustrated in **Fig. 2.**

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Material modeling and element types

Fig. 2. FEA beams modeling

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Material modeling and element types

The FRCC material behavior was modeled in compression and tension and plotted in **Fig 3(a)** and **Fig. 3(b)**, respectively. In addition, steel was modeled using the bilinear strain hardening with yielding and ultimate strength values of 395 MPa and 524 MPa. Finally, the printed beam was constructed using the layer-by-layer method with the interaction between the layers being modeled using the bilinear traction-separation definition. Loading was applied using two reference points coupled to the loading steel plates with the reinforcement cage having an embedded constraint.

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Material modeling and element types

Fig. 3.
Modeling
characteristics

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Validation

The validation of the FEA models was done using two specimens as printed and traditional beams (B2-P and B5-T), including their load-deflection curves and failure modes (**Fig. 4.**). However, it was observed that the experimental and the simulation results matched well with a minimum error range (<2%) including the ultimate strength, ultimate deflection, toughness, and initial stiffness. In addition, the traditional beam failed due to excessive bending action while the printed beam failed due to the interfacial shear stresses induced between the layers and extends from the supporting plates toward the loading plates location, as illustrated in **Fig. 4.**

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Validation

(a) B5-T

(b) B2-P

Fig. 4. Load-deflection curves and failure modes validation

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Results and Discussion (Load-deflection curves)

The load-deflection curves of the eighteen printed beams are presented in **Fig. 5** within six main groups. The model's designation appears as follows: the (PB) refers to a printed beam, the second letter (C) refers to the FRCC compressive strength in MPa, the third letter (S) refers to the shear span value in mm, and the final letter (H) refers to the height of the beam in mm. Observing **Fig. 5** reveals that a significant effect was recorded by the FRCC compressive strength where an increased load capacity and reduced ultimate deflection were associated with increasing the FRCC strength or increasing the beam depth. Moreover, increasing the shear span reduces the failure brittleness and increases the beam ductility.

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Results and Discussion (Load-deflection curves)

Fig. 5. Load-deflection curves

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Results and Discussion (Failure modes)

The failure modes of the printed beams with various conditions are presented in **Fig. 6** and compared to each other using different nine cases. However, beams with different FRCC compressive strengths experienced similar cracking patterns while the shear span and the beam depth have non-uniform behavior. Generally, beams with smaller depths (120 mm) show more ductile behavior with a concrete compression failure mode between the loading points. Besides, increasing the depth of the beam increases the induced shear stresses and results in interlayer shear failure modes. Finally, increasing the shear span widens the failure area and, in some cases, the beam bottom sides were also crushed.

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Results and Discussion (Failure modes)

Fig. 6. Failure modes of the printed beams

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Results and Discussion (Shear span effect)

The structural characteristics of the printed beams were evaluated with respect to the effect of their shear span, including the ultimate load and their corresponding deflection, initial stiffness, and toughness, as shown in **Fig. 7(a)**. Toughness was calculated as the area under the load-deflection curves (**Fig. 5**) while initial stiffness reflects the slope of the linear part

Generally, the shear span of the four-point loading is located at a distance equal to one-third of the loading span. Therefore, the value of each structural measure was normalized with respect to the value corresponding to the four-point loading, as appears in **Fig. 7(a)**. It could be stated that increasing the shear span increases the ultimate deflection values up to 60% compared to an approximate toughness capacity regardless of the shear span value. In contrast, the ultimate load values and the initial stiffness were significantly reduced up to 30% and 50%, respectively.

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Results and Discussion (Shear span effect)

(a) Shear span effect

(b) FRCC compressive strength effect

Fig. 7. Shear span and FRCC strength effect

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Results and Discussion (FRCC compressive strength effect)

The compressive strength effect of the FRCC layers utilized in the printed beams was evaluated in **Fig. 7(b)** for all the structural performance characteristics at different shear span values. Results were normalized between the beam capacities corresponding to a 20 MPa FRCC compressive strength increase (from 23.2 MPa to 43.2 MPa). It could be stated that increasing FRCC strength has a general behavior depending mainly on the shear span value where the ultimate load and the ultimate deflection are affected similarly. Generally, larger percentages were recorded for the ultimate load up to a 90% increase compared to only a 25% increase for the ultimate deflection. On the other hand, the initial stiffness and toughness were minorly affected

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Results and Discussion (Beam depth effect)

The behavior of the 3D printed beams was evaluated depending on the depth effect where an effect was observed for the FRCC compressive strength. The values were normalized with respect to a printed beam with 120 mm depth and plotted in **Fig. 8**. However, large normalized percentages were recorded for the initial stiffness capacity of up to ten times corresponding to a depth increase of 2.3 times. In addition, the ultimate load was increased by four times compared to a 75% reduction for the ultimate deflection.

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Results and Discussion (Shear span effect)

Fig. 8. Beam depth effect

Conclusions

1

The failure mode of the 3D printed beams depends on the overall depth of the beam where an interfacial shear failure was observed for beams with high depths and turned into concrete crushing for beams with lower depths

2

The FRCC compressive strength has a negligible effect on the structural behavior of 3D printed beams with various shear spans where the normalized percentages were similar

3

The amount of absorbed energy was constant for beams with different shear span ratios where the ultimate load and ultimate deflections were increased and decreased proportionally to keep a similar area under the load-deflection curves.

4

The overall depth of the beam has a major role in controlling the beam capacity that could be increased up to four times upon increasing the printed beam depth by 2.3 times compared to ten times for the initial stiffness

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Acknowledgment

Part of this research was supported by the ADDOPTML (ADDitively Manufactured OPTimized Structures by Means of Machine Learning) project (No: 101007595) belonging to the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA) Re-search and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE) H2020-MSCA-RISE-2020. Their support is highly acknowledged. The authors would also like to thank the Jordan University of Science and Technology (JUST) for its support as a part-ner organization in the ADDOPTML project.

Thank you

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Bara'a R. Alnemrawi^{1*}, Rajai Z. Al-Rousan¹, Khairedin M. Abdalla¹, and Nikos Lagaros²

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, Engineering, Jordan university of science and technology, P.O. Box 3030, Irbid 22110, Jordan

bralnemrawi@eng.just.edu.jo, rzalrousan@just.edu.jo, abdallakhairedin@yahoo.com

²School of Structural Engineering, National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), 15780 Zografou, Greece

nlagaros@central.ntua.gr

ABSTRACT

Increasing attention was paid to three-dimensional (3D) printing technology in the construction, architecture, and medical care sectors. However, the utilization of cementitious composites in 3D concrete printing was increased to upgrade the structural behavior of the printed members. In contrast, difficulties and uncertainties still exist regarding the reinforcement method of the printed members with other induced challenges regarding the cost efficiency and sustainability concerns. This study evaluates the structural performance of 3D printed beams with fiber-reinforced cementitious composite (FRCC) and anchoring reinforcement using the method of finite element analysis (FEA). A total of eighteen beams were simulated with different shear spans (400, 500, and 575 mm), overall depth (120, 200, and 276 mm), and FRCC compressive strengths (23.2 and 43.2 MPa). The behavior was reported for all models in terms of the ultimate load and its corresponding deflection, initial stiffness, toughness, and failure modes. Results were presented as general guidelines to highlight the effect of the examined parameters to provide the scientists and engineers with a wide knowledge of the printing field, mitigating the required time and cost. It was found that increasing the shear span increases the beam's ultimate deflection and reduces its capacity. Moreover, increasing the depth of the beams has various effects on the failure mode and the deflection values where beams with lower depths sustain larger deflections compared to the deeper ones.

* The asterisk denotes the presenting author.